
Prof Carlos Alfredo Lopes de Carvalho

Graduated in Agronomic Engineering, Education Specialist and Master in Agricultural Sciences from the Federal University of Bahia. PhD in Sciences with an emphasis on Entomology from the University of São Paulo. Full Professor at the Federal University of Recôncavo da Bahia, Member of the Bahia Academy of Sciences and the Brazilian Academy of Agronomic Science. CNPq Researcher. Leader of the Insecta Research Group.

ACTIONS OF THE INSECTA RESEARCH GROUP (UFRB) WITHIN THE SCOPE OF BEESNESS PROJECT: ACADEMIC MOBILITY AND PESTICIDE TRIALS

Carlos A. L. de Carvalho^{1,3*}, Jaíne S. Rebouças^{1,3*}, Jefferson A. dos Santos^{1,3}, Joilson da C. Santana², Erislan F. Santos², Erika O. S. Farias², Maiara J. M. Caldas^{1,3}, Maria A. P. de C. Costa^{1,3}.

¹ Postgraduate Program in Agricultural Sciences, Federal University of the Recôncavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

² Undergraduate Student in Agronomy, Federal University of the Recôncavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

³ Insecta Research Group, Center for Agricultural, Environmental and Biological Sciences, Federal University of the Recôncavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

* Corresponding author: calfredo@ufrb.edu.br

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Abstract

The negotiations for the participation of the INSECTA Research Group from the Federal University of Recôncavo da Bahia (UFRB) commenced during the Symposium on Bees and Agriculture: Food Production and Pesticides, organized by the Postgraduate Program in Ecology and Evolution at the State University of Feira de Santana. At this event, Dr. Carlos Alfredo Carvalho, coordinator of the INSECTA Group, presented a lecture on the lethal and sublethal effects of pesticides on *Melipona* and *Tetragonisca*,

moderated by Dr. Cândida Aguiar. Following this lecture, Dr. Aline Andrade from the Federal University of Vale do São Francisco facilitated discussions with the BeesNess Project leaders, Dr. Laura Guimarães and Dr. Nuno Ferreira. Given INSECTA's ongoing research on the health and behavior of bees and other insects, which encompassed studies on chemical and biological stressors, adjustments were quickly made for its involvement in BeesNess, particularly incorporating students from the Postgraduate Program in Agricultural Sciences at UFRB. A series of meetings between Dr. Nuno Ferreira (CIIMAR) and Dr. Ana Teresa Guimarães from the State University of Western Paraná (UNIOESTE) and the INSECTA team, including Dr. Maria Angelica Costa and postgraduate and undergraduate students, were pivotal in defining the active ingredients, contamination pathways, and concentrations to be investigated. This collaboration fostered a robust partnership with Dr. Ana Guimarães; team, enhancing academic mobility for students across both institutions and strengthening the cooperation network. The project focused on three stingless bee species (*Melipona quadrifasciata*, *Nannotrigona testaceicornis*, and *Tetragonisca angustula*) and examined the effects of the active ingredients triflumizole, fenpyroximate, and lambda-cyhalothrin through three contamination routes: ingestion, topical application, and contact with contaminated surfaces, assessing both lethal and sublethal effects. The findings contributed to Master's dissertations and a Doctoral thesis in Agricultural Sciences at UFRB, enhancing scientific knowledge, training human resources, and deepening understanding of bee community dynamics in the caatinga biome, ultimately benefiting all participants in the project.

References

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